

PREPRINT

Uplifting Corona Fictions: *No tengas miedo, Ya pasará* and *Andrà tutto bene*¹

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Abstract

The Covid-19 pandemic continuously affects people around the world, exposing the already existing social interconnectedness and economic interdependencies of our times. Revisiting pandemic fiction, as well as, crises narratives in literature and other cultural productions in general, has suddenly become a coping strategy to counteract the effects of physical distancing, but in particular the experiences of lockdowns.

Interestingly, since the early stages of the pandemic in the Western world in spring 2020, numerous artists have not only dissected the reality of confinement across diverse genres but more so provided the public with uplifting content in various audiovisual formats – such as short films, web series, and music videos.

In this article we will mainly take on the latter producing material *about* the pandemic *during* the pandemic, portraying the human need for connection, uplifting narratives and images. Across national, cultural, and linguistic borders, Corona Fictions (cf. Research Group *Pandemic Fictions* 2020) demonstrate how fragile our social fabric is while, at the same time, strengthening the feeling of solidarity, togetherness/ unity, and cohesion. Hence, this article will examine Corona Fictions music videos for their understanding and depiction of uplifting narratives in these challenging times.

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Introduction

*Oh, I know that there'll be better days
Oh, that sunshine 'bout to come my way
May we never ever shed
Another tear for today
'Cause oh, I know that
There'll be better days*

(“Better Days”
by OneRepublic, 25.03.2020)

*Ritorerà l'abbraccio tra la gente
Il sole sulla pelle tornerà
La libertà di correre per strada
Baciarsi alla fermata e a un tratto
Guardarsi negli occhi per poi dire
(dire) Andrà tutto bene (bene)
Andrà tutto bene (bene)*

(“Andrà tutto bene” by Elisa ft.
Tommaso Paradiso, 10.04.2020)

*Andrà tutto bene
Vai ficar tudo bem
Everything will be alright
Andrà tutto bene
Tout ira bien
Everything will be alright*

(“Andrà Tutto Bene”
by Cristóvam, 25.03.2020)

While the Anglophone world (cf. OneRepublic 2020/ 2022) is broadly known for songs released at the beginning of the first wave of a global lockdown in 2020, musicians around the world – unsurprisingly – released their ‘lockdown music’³ in other languages as well. For example, three song titles in Romance languages strengthen people’s beliefs that they do not need to be afraid (Span. *No tengas miedo* by El Canijo de Jerez), that nothing (negative) will stay the same/ bad things will pass (Span. *Ya pasará*), and that, most of all, everything will be alright (Ital. *Andrà tutto bene*⁴). Even though all three songs have been published via music video on YouTube within the first year of the Covid-19 pandemic, not all of their creators intentionally planned on releasing pandemic songs (or as Fink et al. 2021 call them ‘coronamusic’; or ‘Corona Clips’, cf. Ziv/ Hollander-Shabtai 2022). Hence, the corpus songs have been chosen a) due to their release in 2020 (during or after lockdown), b) due to originating in Romance languages and/ or cultures, and c) due to their uplifting nature (lyrics⁵ as well as music video in general). Focusing on a mainly cultural studies perspective, the influence of music itself as a significant tool to regulate one’s mood has not been considered as there have already been numerous studies (see e.g. Hennessy et al. 2021; Martínez-Castilla et al. 2021; Fink et al. 2021) that discerned similar effects considering a ‘coronamusic’ corpus which we also regard as part

³ “Music is a cultural product, a means of communication, created within a social context.” (Ziv/ Hollander-Shabtai 2022: 477).

⁴ We investigated Jack Savoretti’s (2020) *Andrà tutto bene*. However, Elisa (2020) also published a song with the same title (see quote above. Engl. “It will return the embrace among the people/ The sun on the skin will return/ The freedom to run down the street/ To kiss at a bus stop and suddenly/ To look into each other’s eyes and say/ It will be alright/ It will be alright.”; authors’ translation).

⁵ “Music with lyrics, in particular, can be attributed with a specifically large coping potential given that it may combine topicality and social surrogacy with music’s ability to influence peoples’ emotions and provide Solace [capital letter in original]. Engagement with coronamusic may thus constitute the musical equivalent of approach coping [...]” (Fink et al. 2021: 9).

of what we call Corona Fictions⁶. What these studies confirm, is therefore highly relevant and applicable to the corpus of this article, as

[t]he attractiveness and coping potential of coronamusic may primarily lie in its characteristic as a medium that explicitly addresses the COVID-19 pandemic and its consequences on people’s lives and feelings. Coronamusic covers a broad range of topics, with various emotional tones, in an often creative and aesthetically appealing way. (Fink et al. 2021: 9)

As our Corona Fictions research project embraces a much larger scope of texts in a multimodal and audiovisual way, the intention of this particular selection is to demonstrate how differently (yet similarly in their effect on mood) music videos portray and/ or inspire a positive approach on the hardships and crises of life. Although their length does not compare to a theme-related fictional feature film or novel, their audiovisual portraits of the Covid-19 pandemic more so compare to the powerful creation of narratives in the condensed form of Corona Fictions poetry. Popular culture functioning as an early warning system (Ger. ‘Frühwarnsystem’) may early on detect societal grievances (cf. Newiak 2020: 21), hence offering the awareness to counteract them⁷. Apart from recent studies related to mood regulation and well-being during the pandemic, “there are relatively few studies on how individuals use music to regulate their emotions effectively in response to an acute major stressor, such as in the context of a significant, global event” (Hennessy et al. 2021: 2). Thus, “[t]he COVID-19 pandemic provides a unique opportunity in which to study universal responses to a singular, unifying stressor on a grand scale” (ibid.).

No matter if through enjoying the beauty of nature (in *No tengas miedo*), showing images of solidarity and the need for a strong social cohesion⁸ (in *Ya pasará* and *Andrà tutto bene*), the common themes are to remind people of the good and reinforce social connections. Corona Fictions music’s positive outlook on life in times of crisis fostered social stability, as Lauren

⁶ “Corona Fictions [...] emerge during the COVID-19 pandemic and negotiate the latter in their stories, continuing in parts the tradition of creating pandemic fiction. We argue that Corona Fictions reactivate certain structures and elements in the form of metanarratives. The pandemic produced collective experiences which can be understood as transnational and transcultural phenomena translating into the crisis while simultaneously tapping into existing pandemic narratives.” (Obermayr/ Völkl 2022: 4).

⁷ Although not uplifting and, thus, not focus of this investigation, interestingly “Zullo (1991) found that the frequency of pessimistic rumination in popular song lyrics predicted economic downturns with a 1- to 2-year lead” (Putter et al. 2022: 1283; cf. Zullo 1991).

⁸ Social cohesion (cf. Council of Europe 2005: 63) is based on the well-being and shared responsibility of its citizens as well as the integrity of civic values; more importantly, however, it demands feeding into the collective energy by practicing abundant mutual moral support in a cohesive society (cf. Manca 2014: 6026).

Fink and her colleagues (2021) suggest in their study on “Viral tunes: changes in musical behaviours and interest in coronamusic predict socio-emotional coping during COVID-19 lockdown” as follows:

Drawing on data from demographically representative samples in six countries from three continents, we showed that more than half of the surveyed adult population engaged with music as a strategy for coping with emotional and social stressors in the context of the first COVID-19 lockdown in early 2020 (mid-April through mid-May). [...] [W]e showed that it was not the music itself that served as a coping aid, but the purposeful ways people engaged and interacted with it (i.e., their music-related behaviour). In particular, people who had been emotionally affected by the crisis were more likely to change their musical behaviours. Self-reported coping via listening to or making music was mainly predicted by changes in behavioural adaptations in the functions and situations of musical engagement, as well as in music selection behaviour. In particular, an interest in coronamusic was the strongest predictor of socio-emotional coping; demographic factors and more stable individual traits played a smaller role. (Fink 2021: 8)

While the above-mentioned research focused on differences between listening to music versus music-making, this article rather aims to focus on the emotionally uplifting factors for people’s well-being⁹ in consuming Corona Fictions music videos as cultural products on a narratological macro and micro level. Hereby, the main intersecting perspectives are twofold:

- a) How do Corona Fictions music videos narrate pandemic experiences?
- b) In what ways does the emotional/narratological uplifting occur and where can it be detected in textual and audiovisual cues¹⁰?

Through a cultural studies lens, this article further aims to demonstrate how mainly Romance speaking music videos equally take on a significant and socially influential role when it comes to coping with pandemic challenges. The idea of music being strongly intertwined with how we feel, is not new – neither is the participatory and communicative nature of music-making (cf. Fink et al. 2021: 9). Hence, “understanding the relationship between music and well-being is particularly relevant during crisis scenarios such as the pandemic” (Alvarez-Cueva 2022: 7). As Priscila Alvarez-Cueva (2022: 15) further points out,

⁹ In Spain and Italy, for example, listening to music had a significantly positive impact on people’s perceived well-being (cf. Martínez-Castilla et al. 2021: 3). Alvarez-Cueva (2022: 8) “understands well-being as ‘the series of momentary affective states that occur through time’ (Stone & Mackie, 2013, p.29) that may impact both individual and social.”

¹⁰ An in-depth investigation of specific musical cues was out of scope for this contribution and is up for more investigation.

music relates to individual and social well-being. Music helped people navigate the situation by empowering them in their individual and collective spheres, while they were learning how to prevent contagion, appealing to emotions that create a positive view of the crisis. This lesson might help us grow and build a better future. In sum, the music of both amateur and professional artists produced in the pandemic evoked solidarity and kindness, thus helping people remain calm and providing them with the faith they needed to face the crisis.

Pastora Martínez-Castilla and her colleagues (2021: 4) identified four well-being goals: “diversion from the crisis, release and venting of negative emotions (e.g., stress, anxiety, and anger), enjoyment and maintaining good mood, and reducing loneliness and creating a sense of ‘togetherness.’”. Thus, people used music to regulate their emotions, e.g. “such as finding solace, for mental contemplation, and feeling intense emotions, highlighting the different strategies we rely on when anticipating a stressful outcome versus experiencing that outcome” (Hennessy et al. 2021: 13). Briefly, music (videos) functioned as a valve for emotional energy, as individuals tried to navigate the disruptive nature of the pandemic.

This article offers a glimpse into the power of fictional cultural productions in times of crises. Firstly, we will establish the effect of music on mood regulation and well-being, and, secondly, on enhancing social cohesion. Thirdly, we will take a closer look at this uplifting nature – whether by using textual or (audio) visual cues – in the three above-mentioned Corona Fictions music video examples *No tengas miedo*, *Ya pasará*, and *Andrà tutto bene*. Although pandemic challenges inspired most (not all) of these narratives, they tell fictional stories of overcoming obstacles and keeping the glue of the social fabric intact by reminding us of the important role each individual has within society at large.

Corona Fictions Music Videos Promoting Emotional Well-Being and Social Cohesion during the Pandemic

[M]usic is highly efficient in regulating mood, defining self-identity, followed by reducing loneliness and creating a sense of togetherness. Music was found to be most efficient at attaining the goal of enjoyment and maintaining a good mood.
(Granot et al. 2021: 16f.).

The United Nations Department of Global Communications (cf. United Nations 2020/ 2022) early on pointed out the uplifting effect of music practices and music videos gone viral during the pandemic. The e.g. Spanish group Stay Homas situated in Barcelona, actively playing music and singing together on their roof top terrace – as one of many examples mentioned by the UN

(ibid.) – tackles the restrictive nature of the pandemic in an artistic way via lyrics of feeling like an encaged bird¹¹ (“Me siento un pájaro enjaulado” in *Ya no puedo más*, Stay Homas 2020/ 2022) but at the same time expresses the longing for singing, laughing, looking at someone and going out dancing together (“Yo quiero cantarte, reírte, mirarte, sacarte a bailar”; ibid.). Early on during the Covid-19 pandemic, four sections for song classifications have been identified (cf. United Nations 2020/ 2022; Alvarez-Cueva 2022: 9) as follows: a) viral music from the initial period of Covid-19, b) online festivals, c) old songs as anthems, and d) UN professional collaborations. Furthermore, Marcel Vejmelka und Timo Obergöker (2021) in *Coronavirus and Pop Culture in French, Spanish and Portuguese-Speaking Cultures* discuss the following four groups of song classifications focussed on a narratological macro level: a) lockdown songs (‘Lockdown-Lieder’; songs narrating and portraying the lockdown), b) stay-at-home songs (‘Stay-at-home Lieder’, songs strengthening a positive attitude towards lockdown while calling to stay at home), c) mostly covered songs for charity (‘Charity-Lieder’, calling for mutual support and solidarity), as well as d) ‘the song is the dance’ (including dance challenges such as ‘Jerusalema’)¹².

Since the first mentioned classifications of the categories for ‘coronamusic’ or ‘pandemic tunes’ (cf. Fink et al. 2021) elaborate more on dissemination and topicality, rather than an emotional impact, for the ‘uplifting effect’ we additionally took into consideration more suitable classifications in Priscila Alvarez-Cueva and her colleagues’ (Alvarez-Cueva et al. 2020: 67) article “Las narraciones de la cuarentena durante la crisis de la COVID-19 a través de la música: emociones y actividades compartidas por Stay Homas¹³”.

These researchers investigated songs by the Catalan trio Stay Homas that takes up the theme of “Desconfinamiento” (Engl. “Deconfinement”) and identify “five categories of elements that relate to a social reality lived within the time of quarantine in Barcelona”. On a narratological micro level they include a) wishes (‘deseos’; returning to known activities like having coffee with friends), b) emotions (‘emociones’; four subcategories of feelings: positive, negative, uncertain, and of longing/nostalgic¹⁴ nature), c) people (‘personas’; particularly family and

¹¹ Similarly, this reference also exists – as its title suggests – in *Aves Enjauladas* (Rozalen 2020/ 2022).

¹² For more examples also see Völkl/ Obermayr (2022).

¹³ Engl. “Narratives of quarantine during the COVID-19 crisis through music: emotions and activities shared by Stay Homas” (authors’ translation).

¹⁴ According to Granot and colleagues (2021: 17), “[n]ostalgia, with its bitter-sweet qualia, is often associated with autobiographical memory, high arousal, familiarity, liking, and strong mixed emotions (Michels-Ratliff and Ennis, 2016), especially in sad music (Vuoskoski and Eerola, 2012)”.

friends), d) practices (‘prácticas’; activities possible during lockdown such as yoga, painting, cooking, etc.) and e) reflections (‘reflexiones’; reflecting on one’s life with intentions of change for a brighter and hopeful future) (cf. *ibid.*: 71-75)¹⁵. These emerging characteristics “connect with emotions and generate responses of interest, empathy, and solidarity beyond the variants of age, gender, and location” (*ibid.*: 67), thus, allow for useful categories to also apply to other artists’ songs (re)created/ covered during the pandemic.

We understand these songs and their music videos as part of a larger very diverse, multimodal, literary and audiovisual Corona Fictions corpus of cultural productions¹⁶ impacting societies around the world. As Hennessy and her colleagues (2021: 12) stated, “music had a salubrious impact on people during a global crisis that transcended potential differences in culture and governmental response to the pandemic”. Furthermore, their study specifically “showed that across four different countries on three different continents, listening to music to regulate mood was a strong predictor of affective well-being during the COVID-19 pandemic. While the mechanisms by which music is able to improve mood may change across people, the fundamental result is the same” (*ibid.*: 14). The disruption¹⁷ of everyday life, social relations, and freedom of movement – commonly used as a form of legal and social punishment when e.g. considering prison – can be identified as a common stressor on a global level, demanding for a valve or transformational tool. Furthermore, “research shows that under stressful circumstances such as those experienced during the COVID-19 lockdown in Spain, musical

¹⁵ This study combined inductive with deductive methods, meaning that the inductive analysis allowed for three additional categories among lyrics and performances identified in the process to emerge: (f) education/entertainment, (g) allusion to war, and (h) nationalism (cf. Alvarez-Cueva 2022: 7; 10).

¹⁶ “The social distancing rules have an indisputable effect on social practices. They not only transform what was hitherto considered ‘normal’ behaviour (handshakes, hugs, physical contact in general) into inappropriate or even dangerous practices but simultaneously stimulate hope and solidarity in cultural production, particularly in music videos, e.g. in Carlos Rivera’s (2020) *Ya pasará* when focusing on overcoming the current corona crisis (‘Sin dudar sé que puedo aguantar//Sé que puedo volver a empezar//Ya pasará la tempestad//Traerá la calma//Y lo que hoy duele sanará//Ya lo verás que este final//Será el principio//Y lo mejor podrá pasar’). Whereas behaviour considered as unusual in some parts of the world is represented as ‘normal’ in Corona Fictions. [...] In Quebec, Mat Cyr and Jérémy Demay point out the new hygiene practices, among other confinement issues, in their song *Le CoronaVirus* (2020) [...]. Numerous narratives focus on the work of medical staff during the corona crisis, requiring a special dedication to the community. Vanesa Martín’s music video *Un Canto [sic] a la vida* (2020) broaches this necessity of people working together and in her YouTube song description explicitly calls ‘a la unión, la empatía y la solidaridad’. [...] To express gratitude towards the essential service workers, the practice of clapping established across national borders [and] at a certain time of the day became a collective experience, thereby reinforcing the sense of community. [...] The collective clapping is illustrated in [...] numerous music videos, such as *Un Canto [sic] a la vida* (2020) and in Jack Savoretti’s first song in Italian *Andrà tutto bene* (2020). Thus, through cultural production and/or collective action, the crisis can have a unifying effect.” (Research Group *Pandemic Fictions** 2020: 333f.).

¹⁷ “[R]esearch has suggested that it is the everyday life disruption caused by the lockdowns, and not the COVID-19 incidence rates, what leads individuals to choose specific music patterns with the aim of reducing negative affect (Yeung, 2020).” (Martínez-Castilla 2021: 11).

training can enhance the usefulness of music for wellbeing promotion“ (Martínez-Castilla et al. 2021). Thus, consuming Corona Fictions music videos offered one of these tools, seemingly even more effective for experienced musicians. Interestingly, “[n]one of the COVID-19 context-related variables had significant effects (living in a region with a high COVID-19 impact, perception of belonging to a risk group, being alone, having caring responsibilities” (Martínez-Castilla et al. 2021) when it comes to using music to reach well-being goals. Rather it was some personal variables – e.g. musical training and the age factor – making a significant difference. Despite the elderly being at higher risk of severe infection, “[t]he youngest participants reported higher efficacy of music in obtaining feelings of enjoyment and maintaining their good mood and to get distracted from the crisis [...]” (ibid. 9).

Regardless of age, concerning coping through musical engagement, Fink and colleagues (2021: 8-9) identified the four following themes:

- a) “During the COVID-19 lockdown, people have turned to music for regulating their emotions [bold in original]”.
- b) “People experiencing different types of emotional changes showed different patterns of musical engagement [bold in original].”
- c) “Music listening and music making may provide different coping potentials [bold in original].”
- d) “Coronamusic played a key role in socio-emotional coping [bold in original].”

Arguably, most significant for this article were a) and d): a) proving that people use music to regulate emotions, and d) that specifically ‘coronamusic’, in this case, Corona Fictions music videos have a great impact on socio-emotionally coping with the pandemic. Particularly the disruptive nature of lockdown was confronted by this means, since music listening increased significantly during that time (cf. Fink et al. 2021: 8). Limited opportunities for social interactions and support animated people to “put music in the role of a compassionate vis-à-vis, with Solace-related [capital in original] functions” (ibid.: 9). Regarding c), the potentials in making music versus listening to music vary: making music requires agency and is a way of expressing oneself, “thus [it] tends to merge with the performer” (Fink et al. 2021: 9). Reducing negative emotions by listening to music, on the contrary, “implies an expectation that the music is the agent, turning to the listener and addressing them in their distress” (ibid.).

Particularly at the beginning of the Covid-19 pandemic, music videos of different categories (as mentioned above), have impacted human behaviour. On the one hand, they inspired and

supported to spread information on hygiene measures¹⁸ to combat the virus; on the other, they offered a way to combat anxiety, loneliness, and other negative emotions that have increased due to the pandemic. Mood regulation (cf. Hennessy et al. 2021; Martínez-Castilla et al. 2021; Fink et al. 2021; Saarikallio/ Erkkilä 2007¹⁹) is an essential function of music practices, regardless whether we take into consideration actively playing an instrument or singing together online or listening to music to uplift one’s mood to support well-being (cf. Granot et al. 2021). Uplifting, positive lyrics and music video performances were consciously used to counteract anxiety and a feeling of uncertainty due to the crisis. As Alvarez-Cueva (2022: 8) has shown, music indeed made a significant difference²⁰, as it “helped strengthen both individual and social spheres that, in turn, are the basis for well-being”. Moreover, she considers music as an ‘antidote to the effects of the coronavirus’ (cf. *ibid.*) since shared positive emotions through music may reduce the feeling of loneliness and reinforce social bonds (cf. *ibid.*: 11). She furthermore points towards an article by the United Nations (2020/ 2022), summing up music practices during the pandemic as “a source of optimism and solidarity throughout the crisis” (Alvarez-Cueva 2022: 7). As social cohesion is fundamental for a peaceful, inclusive society, stabilizing people’s mood must be regarded as significant contribution to fight the negative consequences of the pandemic. Social media ‘tools’ such as hashtags (e.g. #andratuttobene #musiquecoronavirus #musiquecovid19 #rapcorona #lockdownmusic #coronamusic #quarantinemusic #restezchezvous #quedateencasa; also see Vökl/ Obermayr 2023) support this cohesive idea.

¹⁸ ‘Practices’ (cf. Alvarez-Cueva 2022: 12) represent the narratives primarily used to remind people of the official containment measures and function as a category helping to direct (and/or change) human behavior by mentioning social (but more so physical) distancing or reminding people to stay at home, as can be observed in numerous hashtags in various languages emerging during the first lockdown, all referring to staying at home and following the containment measures set in place globally, e.g. #andratuttobene, #quedateencasa etc. (cf. Vökl/ Obermayr 2022).

¹⁹ “[T]here may be a stronger need for an additional medium for mood regulation in adolescence due to the incomplete acquisition of sophisticated regulatory strategies. The music itself, as a typical feature of adolescent life, may be an easily approachable medium especially for the young. [...] Music proved to be a versatile means for mood regulation. It offered the adolescents resources for increasing and restoring well-being, and made their emotional life more varied and colourful.” (Saarikallio/ Erkkilä 2007: 105).

²⁰ When it comes to strengthening people’s resilience, however, the findings differed. Hence, it has to be mentioned that one study’s findings are astounding, since “[r]esilience was not significantly correlated to music’s efficacy for any of the wellbeing goals. The lack of significance of resilience was unexpected.” (Martínez-Castilla et al. 2021: 7). More investigations in the future are recommended.

Uplifting Corona Fictions Music Videos *No tengas miedo, Ya pasaré, and Andrà tutto bene* – Don’t Be Afraid, everything will be fine!

*Two or three months/ They’re saying on TV/
Be safe in your shelters and soon we’ll be free/
One day we’ll remember the hardest of times/
When distance meant love and it kept us alive.*
“Andrà tutto bene” by Cristóvam (2020/ 2022).

Despite the initially positive prognoses on the duration of the lockdowns in media and political reports during the first year of the pandemic, both the authors/ creators of cultural productions as well as the characters of Corona Fictions were confronted with the ‘first lockdown shock effect’ (cf. Singer et al. 2021; cf. Vökl/ Obermayr 2023). Confined to the private spaces of their homes, their fictional characters either also suffer due to limited social life and restricted activities together while struggling to maintain functioning social bonds (e.g. in *Ya pasaré* and in *Andrà tutto bene*); or they embody protagonists of an almost utopian post-pandemic future (e.g. in *No tengas miedo*). No matter if this positive future is explicitly represented or solely implicitly alluded to, the uplifting effect of the three Corona Fictions music videos of our corpus, can be detected on both a narratological a) macro, and b) micro level:

On a *macro level*, the overall presentation of each of the fictional arcs in the corpus selected offers hope and a positive outlook on the future. Some narratives continuously encourage a positive feeling in the audience on a macro level as *El Canijo de Jerez* (2020/ 2022) has shown in *No tengas miedo*²¹. Others present a supposed solution to a negative situation or feeling, as Carlos Rivera’s (2020/ 2022) *Ya pasaré* demonstrates. This video starts off with negative audiovisual cues of people having to close stores at [00:00:04] and other’s being treated at the hospital at [00:00:18-00:00:30] but ends with clouds disappearing in the sky to let the sunshine through. These images are underlined by lyrics indicating that everything (negative) is temporary, that every ‘storm will pass’ (“Ya pasaré, la tempestad”; [00:03:24]). Similarly, Jack Savoretti’s (2020/ 2022) *Andrà tutto bene* portrays the emptiness in the streets around [00:00:20] before lyrically reassuring us that everything will be all right by citing the song’s title one minute into the song.

²¹ We argue that the original intention of not writing *No tengas miedo* during or because of the pandemic (cf. La Higuera.net 2020/ 2022) does not significantly mean to exclude it from the Corona Fictions corpus, as it was first published during these challenging times, fulfilling the uplifting elements. In times of music videos and specific content being attached to hashtags (cf. Vökl/ Obermayr 2022) going viral, the relatability in terms of pandemic experiences and the uplifting factor on an emotional level in terms of mood regulation underline the significance of these songs amongst Corona Fictions music productions.

Category-wise, we suggest that Rivera’s *Ya pasará* and Savoretti’s *Andrà tutto bene* fall into three main categories of ‘lockdown songs’, indirect ‘stay-at-home songs’, but also into newly created ‘charity songs’ (cf. Vejmelka/ Obergöker 2021), as they called for donations to organisations needing the money to fight the (consequences of) the pandemic. While Rivera (cf. 2020/ 2022) mentioned donating 100% of income of this song to an international organization called Save the Children in the YouTube information below the music video, Savoretti (2020/ 2022) introduced this information on a black background directly in the music video. There he stated that “‘Andrà Tutto Bene’ is Jack Savoretti’s first ever song in Italian and was created during an Instagram live writing session with his Italian fans. All proceeds will be donated to the Policlinico San Martino hospital in Genoa for the project #genovapersanmartino” (ibid. [00:00:06-00:00:20]). He ended the music video by thanking his fans: “This work was made possible with the help of many people who sent their contribution from their homes. The rest of the footage collected was shared online by users or aired by TV networks” (ibid. [00:03:50-00:04:01]).

El Canijo de Jerez’s (2020/ 2022) *No tengas miedo* does not fall into any of the four categories established by Vejmelka/ Obergöker (cf. 2021). This might be due to originally not being written (yet published) explicitly during the pandemic (cf. El Canijo de Jerez y la Banda Magnética 2022).

On a *micro level*, the uplifting *textual cues* (encouraging lyrics²² to endure and persist until feeling better), as well as, the uplifting *audiovisual cues* (lyrics sung and portrayed, as well as, filmic specificities, e.g. warm colours, images of connecting with loved ones etc.) can explicitly be noticed in the corpus selected, each adapted to the overall construction of the macro level. After a close reading of the lyrics and extracting their positive emotions, the narrative function of the audiovisual presentations linked to each song was analyzed: The artists hereby focused on positive elements again, meaning elements uplifting people’s mood. Empathy²³ (feeling the other’s pain), unity and togetherness (either virtually sharing the same space or more so understood as physical proximity amongst humans within the same space), and solidarity

²² Admittedly, as Putter and colleagues also stated in their article, “consideration of both lyrical and musical variables together would further increase our understanding of this topic” (Putter et al. 2022: 1290). However, this is beyond the scope of this article and demands a more music-oriented – less cultural studies oriented – approach.

²³ “[M]uch of the coronamusic repertoire seeks to provide information about the virus and essential hygiene measures in an attractive and convincing way, calling for peoples’ understanding and compliance. [...] [C]oronamusic not only provides empathy to its audience but can also be expected to elicit it and, ultimately, serve as a means to influence human behaviour, problem-solving, and adaptive coping.” (Fink et al. 2021: 9).

emerge as recurring themes to counteract the restrictive nature and feeling of imprisonment of the lockdown. Taking into consideration various elements which Alvarez-Cueva and her colleagues (2020: 71-75) identified in Stay Home’s ‘coronamusic’, as mentioned before, both Rivera’s and Savoretti’s Corona Fictions music videos make use of most of them in an intermingled way, except for the category ‘practices’, which is hardly used in the chosen examples. Only when considering ‘practices’ such as clapping on the balcony²⁴ together, may we also identify it in both clips.

‘Emotions’, including all of the four subcategories of feelings: positive, negative, uncertain, and of longing/ nostalgic nature, can be found in all of the corpus investigated. However, the focus clearly lies on generating uplifting ones via lyrics and music video. Interestingly, “[p]ositive emotions are consistent even when a melancholier melody is used [...]” (Alvarez-Cueva 2022: 11). Even though one must keep in mind cultural differences²⁵ when it comes to music listening behaviours and the significance of lyrics,

positive emotions were fundamental to all the narratives analysed, either because the lyrics made direct references to ‘smile’, ‘hug’, ‘resurge’, or because the videoclips suggested positivity through its presentational style, especially when the screen was split into many spaces where different people were singing together while smiling at the camera. The online interaction due to social distancing measures not only contributed to trying to hold social networks but, particularly in the case of music, permitted the reinforcement of previous ties through the energy that is conveyed in music. (Alvarez-Cueva 2022: 11)

In music videos with their audiovisual components, not only does the music itself address its listeners (as above-mentioned, cf. Fink et al. 2021: 8-9) but more so, the singer/ performer merging with the music, hereby, also addresses them by a) looking directly into the camera (e.g. Carlos Rivera in *Ya pasará*; El Canijo de Jerez and La Mari in *No tengas miedo*), and b) by calling for unity in the lyrics and implementing participatory (audio)visuals (e.g. Jack Savoretti and/ or by including the audience into their video by integrating their snippets from Instagram lives etc. as in *Andrà tutto bene* and *Ya pasará*). Thus, the artists’ overall presentations urge for strengthening social cohesion in their textual, as well as, audiovisual cues. Unsurprisingly, Alvarez-Cueva’s (2022: 15) findings support this, as she argues that “ideas of ‘unity’ were

²⁴ “Italy and Spain saw mass communal singing from home balconies, and Lehman (2021) reported significantly increased streaming of some of the songs concerned.” (Putter et al. 2022: 1281; cf. Lehman 2021).

²⁵ The listeners “degree of interest in lyrics and the types of emotions aroused by lyrics may be important factors to consider within future research” (Putter et al. 2022: 1290f.), since they vary due to cultural differences and diverse strategies for coping with hardships and challenging times.

crucial not only to maintain faith in the future but also to encourage people to think of themselves and others and help them face the situation.”

Marco del Ojo from El Canijo del Jerez and María del Mar Rodríguez Carnero called La Mari from the group Chambao created one of the corpus songs together to uplift and encourage people to get up again after falling. The self-explanatory title ‘No tengas miedo’ (Engl. ‘Don’t be afraid’) already indicates a positive attitude towards the pandemic but its creators additionally explain their intentions explicitly in the information beneath their music video on YouTube uploaded on the channel El Canijo Jerez (2020/ 2022) as follows:

Tres palabras, dos artistas y una canción. Esos son los números mágicos que marcan el nuevo single de El Canijo de Jerez, ‘No tengas miedo’ todo un canto a la esperanza, más necesario ahora que nunca si atendemos a los tiempos que nos ha tocado vivir.²⁶

This music video, directed and produced by Colirio Films (cf. *ibid.*), painted in warm light and soothing colours of a sunrise set in Spanish nature (also see sunrise in *Ya pasará*), counteracts fears with ‘good vibes’ (“buenas vibraciones”, *ibid.*) and – according to the singer – has a clear message that getting up again after falling is the only option there is (“Caerse es necesario. Levantarse, la única opción”; *ibid.*). The song is supposed to function as a healing remedy (“remedio sanador”; *ibid.*), which – unsurprisingly – above-mentioned scientific studies (e.g. Hennessy et al. 2021, Fink et al. 2021, Martínez-Castilla et al. 2021) on music as a mood regulator (listening to it or actively participating in it) generally confirm. *No tengas miedo* is a song dedicated to “todos los soñadores que llenan espacios en blanco²⁷” and strongly encourages its listeners to joyfully embrace the life ahead of us (“saludar a la vida que nos espera por delante”; *ibid.*) because life is better believing that everything turns out alright (“Porque, al final, todo saldrá bien”; *ibid.*).

Canijo de Jerez’ new album “Constelaciones de Humo²⁸” seems inspired by the pandemic since it fits perfectly. At the beginning of the album after the intro, *Esto es una ruina*²⁹ starts off with the lyrics “Dios hizo el mundo y no le salió muy bien/ se le fue de las manos y ya no tiene na’ que hacer/ ahora somos muchos golpeando sin control/ somos lo peor, vamos directo a la

²⁶ Engl. “Three words, two artists and one song. Those are the magic numbers that mark the new single by El Canijo de Jerez, ‘No tengas miedo’ (Engl. ‘Don’t be afraid’) is a song to hope, more necessary now than ever if we consider the times we live in.” (authors’ translation).

²⁷ Engl. “to all the dreamers who fill in the blanks” (authors’ translation).

²⁸ Engl. “Constellations of Smoke” (authors’ translation).

²⁹ Engl. *This is a ruin* (authors’ translation).

extinción³⁰” (Canijo de Jerez 2022). However, it was not intentionally pandemic-related (written in 2018/2019; cf. LaHiguera.net 2020/ 2022) but just originates in a mindset that invites people to embrace all adversities of life with a positive attitude. Therefore, it still takes on the same function to uplift and stays included in our small corpus. The vocabulary used in the lyrics effectively a) enhances positive feelings and b) counteracts negative³¹ feelings such as anxiety, as the following correlating statement from recent studies proves, stating that

[l]onging emotions [...] link with the desire and need to return to a pre-pandemic lifestyle. Through these emotions, it is possible to see how Covid-19 shifted known life worldwide, resulting in the emergence of romanticized references to what people used to do before the pandemic [...]. (Alvarez-Cueva 2022: 10f.)

These ‘romanticized references’ also apply to what Alvarez-Cueva and her colleagues (2020) two years earlier classified as the category ‘wishes’, found in *Ya pasará* where a child looks at a seed after sprouting while the lyrics announce that we will return even stronger than before (“Y volveremos, volveremos, volveremos ¡Más fuertes!”; Carlos Rivera 2020/ 2022 [00:03:42]). Moreover, in *Andrà tutto bene*, the singer Savoretti (2020/ 2022) lyrically ‘wishes’ for people to bloom like a flower in spring and go back to singing (“Quando arriva la primavera/ Sbocceremo come un fiore/ Torneremo a cantare”; [00:02:43-00:02:56]).

Furthermore, all songs selected such as El Canijo de Jerez’s (2020/ 2022) *No tengas miedo* touch upon ‘reflections’ (cf. Alvarez-Cueva et al. 2020: 71-75) on the micro level, singing for a brighter future in a hopeful way. Falling under the category of ‘reflections³²’ (cf. Alvarez-Cueva et al. 2020), this Corona Fictions music video – through its audiovisual cues at the end around [00:02:52-00:03:17] – reflects the unity of the musicians and singers. Five people stand where the singers sat before on the rim of the pool, the sun already up behind them higher than before, thus, we cannot see their faces but only their silhouettes until the camera frame shows

³⁰ Engl. “God made the world and it didn't work out very well/ It got out of hand and He has nothing left to do/ Now there are many of us screwing around without control/ we are the worst, we are heading straight towards extinction”. (authors’ translation).

³¹ “[P]eople who were more severely impacted by the pandemic tended to listen to music that was less loud and energetic and more acoustic. Overall, the people who listened to softer, more acoustic music also reported feeling better as a result of listening to music during the pandemic. Interestingly, people who reported using music to discharge negative feelings actually preferred music that was more energetic and less acoustic, which is consistent with the goal of using music to purge or release negative emotions.” (Hennessy et al. 2021: 13).

³² “[N]umerous [other] music videos envision a time after the corona crisis, underlining the importance of human touch and relationships with loved ones, e.g. in Rozalén’s *Aves enjauladas* (2020) where the singer shifts her focus on what matters to her in the future: ‘Cuando salga de esta iré corriendo a aplaudirte//Sonreiré, le daré las gracias a quién me cuida//Ya nadie se atreverá a burlar lo importante//La calidad de la sanidad será intocable [...] Contagiar mis ganas de vivir y toda mi alegría//Construir, construir [...] Recuerda siempre la lección//Y este será un mundo mejor//Cuando salga de esta iré corriendo a abrazarte”’ (Research Group *Pandemic Fictions** 2020: 336).

the guitarist closer in their respective frame. Almost simultaneously around [00:02:53], the lyrics “Agárrate a la vida que empieza lo bueno/ Nunca te rindas, levántate/ Todo saldrá bien, no tengas miedo” call for ‘taking a chance at life’, and indicate a positive outcome, a ‘new beginning’, encouraging you to ‘never give up/ everything will be alright, don’t be afraid’. Equally, Rivera’s (2020/ 2022) *Ya pasará* refers to this new beginning and positive future just before [00:03:42] (“Ya lo verás, que este final/ Será el principio y lo mejor podrá pasar”). The positive effect of focussing on a better future in situations of crisis or hardship is not only underlined here but moreover stands out in the way Rivera’s song is presented (audio)visually. The sunrise and its orange colouring build a common theme throughout the video, either marking certain lettering, signs, objects such as an orange curtain or the framing/design itself. The strong contrast created by using black and white as dominant colours, allows for any orange coloured scenario/ object to stand out. This orange colouring reinforces the positive connotation of certain words, situations or objects to point out the importance of keeping a positive attitude throughout the pandemic. This feeling intensifies even further by repeatedly contrasting the uplifting parts with frames full of confident and caring medical staff that reminds of the possibility of severe illness but simultaneously radiates enough expertise and confidence to handle the crisis.

Similarly, Savoretti’s (2020/ 2022) song *Andrà tutto bene*³³, as the title indicates in Italian, underlines a positive outcome, particularly by mentioning the physical touch such as finally hugging loved ones again. Thus, it intermingles with the classification for ‘people’. The category ‘people’ identified mainly family and friends, the social nucleus, who were terribly missed during lockdown or even more so solitary confinement (quarantine). As our social bonds and the feeling of belonging to a collective strengthen identity building, having significant people physically present and close for all kinds of activities not only affects social cohesion but simultaneously our individual identity and relationships with others (cf. Alvarez-Cueva et al. 2020: 73). To counteract the mentioned lockdown shock effect, and more specifically

³³ “In Italy in March 2020 the hashtag #andratuttobene emerged during the first weeks of the lockdown. [...] Savoretti’s *Andrà tutto bene* (2020) underlines a positive outcome: ‘Quando finirà tutto//Ci troveremo davanti a un tramonto//Sentiremo più forte//La magia di un momento [...] Andrà tutto bene//Non sentiamoci divisi//C’è ancora tempo per amare//Andrà tutto bene//Siamo distanti ma uniti//Dal desiderio di tornare’. Elisa, as many other artists, uses the phrase *Andrà tutto bene* (2020) as a song title, imagining a similar, more carefree future: ‘Ritournerà//L’abbraccio tra la gente//Il sole sulla pelle tornerà//La libertà//Di correre per strada//Baciarsi alla fermata e a un tratto//Guardarsi negli occhi per poi dire//Andrà tutto bene//Andrà tutto bene’. All these abovementioned Corona Fictions not only distill the importance of human connection, touch, and freedom to move outside, but also indicate the willingness for social change after the lockdown“ (Research Group *Pandemic Fictions** 2020: 336; cf. ELISA Official 2020/ 2022).

isolation, Denis Newiak (cf. 2020: 92f.), points out movie protagonists’ strategies to self-strengthen their resilience during a crisis by keeping a daily routine (i.g. regular meals and sports or other physical activities; *ibid.*: 94), or ‘practices’ (cf. Alvarez-Cueva et al. 2020) possible during confinement, such as clapping or singing on the balcony together. Moreover, keeping social commitments (see category ‘people’; *ibid.*), within the common cultural norms demonstrates the need for human interaction and connection: even if only by upholding the illusion via substitutes as Newiak mentioned (cf. 2020: 96f.), or – in the case of Corona Fictions music videos – by virtually generating social connection via split screens or otherwise integrated film material by different individuals put together to form part of a collective, as can be seen in both *Ya pasará* and *Andrà tutto bene*.

Conclusion

Listening to music (also practising it) in these unprecedented times functioned as a powerful tool in mood regulation and had a salubrious effect on people during the pandemic, regardless of cultural differences and diverse containment measures. Hence, this act of self-care underlines how significantly people’s well-being was impacted by the disease Covid-19, or, more precisely, by the disruptive containment measures taken such as the first lockdown in spring 2020. Cultural production in terms of public events (concerts etc.) came to a sudden halt. However, people frequently turned to literary and audiovisual productions emerging (mainly online) such as Corona Fictions music videos to discharge negative feelings or stimulate positive ones to counteract anxiety, provoke solidarity and a sense of unity despite being physically apart during confinement. As numerous recent above-mentioned studies have shown from a psychological, sociological, and musicological point-of-view, the investigated Corona Fictions music videos equally demonstrate from a cultural studies perspective, how essential creating and consuming fiction can be – particularly in uncertain times. Corona Fictions music videos, thus, play a significant role in narrating pandemic experiences within a larger, multimodal and transmedia Corona Fictions corpus.

The three corpus songs selected for this article – Carlos Rivera’s *Ya pasará* and El Canijo de Jerez’s *No tengas miedo* in Spanish, as well as, Jack Savoretti’s *Andrà tutto bene* in Italian – functioned as main examples for this article. The uplifting effect of these Corona Fictions music videos taken into consideration, can be detected on both a narratological a) macro, and b) micro level:

- a) On a macro level, the narrative either continuously encourages a positive feeling by the overall presentation of the fictional arc – as in El Canijo de Jerez’s *No tengas miedo* – and offers hope and a positive outlook on the future or presents a supposed solution (or better future) to a negative situation or feeling during the pandemic, as demonstrated in Jack Savoretti’s *Andrà tutto bene* and Carlos Rivera’s *Ya pasará*.

- b) On a micro level, the uplifting elements in Corona Fictions music videos can explicitly be noticed in *textual cues* (encouraging lyrics to endure and persist until feeling better) and *audiovisual cues* (lyrics sung and portrayed, as well as, filmic specificities, e.g. warm colours, images of connecting with loved ones etc.). Hereby, empathy, unity (also understood as proximity within the same space), and solidarity emerge as recurring themes to counteract the imprisoned feeling produced by the lockdown, pointing towards the importance of social cohesion and the essence of being human: connection.

In his closing remarks of “‘Washing Hands, Reaching out’ – Popular Music, Digital Leisure and Touch during the COVID-19 pandemic” Eric T. Lehman (2021: 278) said it best: “I will close my eyes and listen to the audience celebrating proximity, unity and togetherness. I will imagine myself there, and dream of future hot, August nights when social distancing vanishes and connecting returns around the cottage campfire”. This raises the question of the pandemic ending: When will Corona Fictions turn from portraying an acute pandemic present to processing a grim pandemic past? When will Corona Fictions creators turn to predominantly imagining a post-pandemic bliss in the near future?

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Corpus Mentioned

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